

31st National IVF Conference

Brno, Czech Republic

One of the most important events in Central Europe about Infertility and IVF was November 9-10 at the **31st Congress of Assisted Reproduction** in Brno, the Czech Republic. Joining the exclusive list of professionals in the field of ART, including the Society of Assisted Reproduction of the Czech Republic and Slovakia, are Medistella co-founders Anna Dostalova and Michaela Novotna. These highly established ladies were honored to represent their collaboration in the very distinct research project, B2-InF, at this 2-day event.

The B2-InF project helps to align the public's perceptions of ART with that of the government in hopes of exacting change to bring better services, support, and awareness of Assisted Reproduction. This project fits in line with the events discussions surrounding ART including different medicines, approaches and evolving technologies, presenting of the data available from our National Register of ART, plus news and updates from ESHRE. Medistella's presence was welcomed as they answered questions about B2-InF project objectives as their expertise and experience in ART make them acutely aware of all sides and they are able to provide valuable detail.

At the event, the highly respected and specialized audience of leaders in the field agreed that the B2InF project is extremely important and that the results will have a great impactful to the future of ART. In addition to deep and interesting discussions about the project goals, Medistella was able to address the motivation of donors, the unique perspectives between genders and sociocultural views, and ways to prevent issues with fertility. Anna and Michaela were also proud to bring attention to the specialized communities of Czech and Slovakia, their hometowns.

The poster is available for download in [Zenodo](#).

